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Background Document for the Technical Dialogue on «Knowledge Management and Capacity Building in Support of the Regional Ocean Governance Strategy» (Western Indian Ocean)

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Knowledge Management and Capacity Building Cluster (KM&CB Cluster) is amongst four interrelated clusters that were identified in 2022 by the Regional Ocean Governance (ROGS) Task Force (TF) as crucial elements of the ROGS for the WIO region. Specifically, the Knowledge Management and Capacity Building Cluster was identified as a cross-cutting issue in the Strategy. Knowledge Management (KM) and Capacity Building (CB) are closely related concepts that play crucial roles in decision making and management. Broadly speaking, knowledge management is the creation, coordination, transfer, and integration of knowledge to make it accessible and usable by specific stakeholders. For this paper, knowledge management deals extensively with sciences and science education at all levels and should be understood in terms of its role in assisting public decision-making in relation to the marine and coastal environment. Knowledge management contributes to capacity building by ensuring that knowledge is systematically captured, shared, and utilized for learning and improvement.

KM&CB Cluster (in the ROGS) operates within the framework of the mandate of the Nairobi Convention¹ (NC) and the actions taken under the latter's umbrella. By virtue of this mandate, the Nairobi Convention Secretariat has a supporting role to play in the human, physical and biological sciences describing coastal

and marine environments and their trajectories, within the marine waters included in its scope. This role is strengthened by the existence of four protocols, at different stages of development².

For the 10 WIO States (Contracting parties), fulfilling these environmental obligations with regard to the Convention and Protocols often requires national or cooperative scientific expertise and resources, which should be easily mobilized. In order to implement best practices in WIO governance, ocean management practitioners must be innovative and must learn from the lessons that are taught in practical and real-time situations. In brief, practitioners must constantly enhance their knowledge and skills. To this end, investments in systems, databases and network structures need to be made to develop a culture of learning from prior knowledge and also from current best practices. Facilitating this task remains an ongoing concern. Regional reports on various topics, by using common indicators on the state of the coastal environment or on national institutional activities, were produced collaboratively by institutions in the region, e.g. the Regional State of the Coast Report 2015 and Western Indian Ocean Marine Protected Areas Outlook 2021. In this brief, we define the priority areas of knowledge identified by the KM&CB cluster, potentially to be included as part of future Work Programmes, and we highlight the infrastructures

¹ the Nairobi Convention for the Protection, Management and Development of the Marine and Coastal Environment of the Western Indian Ocean Region

² The Protocol Concerning Protected Areas and Wild Fauna and Flora in the Eastern African Region and the Protocol Concerning Cooperation in Combating Marine Pollution in Cases of Emergency in the Eastern African Region, entered into force on 30th May 1996 and is undergoing revision. The Protocol for the Protection of the Marine and Coastal Environment of the Western Indian Ocean from Land-Based Sources and Activities, adopted 31st March, 2010, has been undergoing ratification by Contracting Parties and will enter into force as soon as it is ratified by 6 countries. The Integrated Coastal Zone Management Protocol for the Western Indian Ocean was adopted in September 2023 and is awaiting ratification by Contracting Parties to enter into force.

and mechanisms that can support the action of the Nairobi Convention to consider scientific aspects in ocean governance.

2. KEY AREAS OF KNOWLEDGE

In the past decade, the marine environment knowledge was mostly restricted to coastal zones, which include deltas, coastlines, and coastal waters of State parties. It has spread towards the offshore regions of the States' EEZ (and even in the WIO high seas). New sets of information now exist to understand the linkages between offshore and inshore environments, and to develop ecosystem-based approaches under increasing anthropogenic pressures (fisheries, pollution, habitat degradation, climate change etc.). However, the information on the offshore domain is still largely incomplete. The Nairobi Convention has taken legal decisions in recent years to support issues related to marine science that are able to support public policies for conservation in the WIO (ecological productivity conditions in particular). Along the ROGS, the KM&BC Cluster has identified flagship sectors that should be strengthened to develop effective science supporting governance mechanisms in this area.

2.1. Summary of priority areas - building up ocean knowledge

Ocean knowledge should take a central role in planning for a sustainable WIO future including understanding and managing the aquatic systems; weather and climate systems; biodiversity; and the links between the Ocean and human societies, economy, health, and wellbeing.

The Ocean Decade Africa Roadmap, launched on the occasion of the African Conference on Priority Setting and Partnership Development for the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, provides both an aspirational vision and a solid plan for diverse stakeholders to convene around a common set of priorities for the implementation of the Decade at the African continental level and in adjacent island states. The WIO region is committed to the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030 and the following knowledge needs have been identified:

Common use of ocean & oceanic sciences

- ∫ Supporting sustainable fisheries in the WIO based on a larger spectrum of topics: a) the role and effectiveness of MPAs to sustain both fisheries and tourism, the role of transboundary environments and resources; b) the study of connectivity patterns between exploited coastal ecosystems and ABNJ seamounts, submarine structures, and MPAs; c) ensuring economic viability of mechanisms; d) ensuring that regulations offer a range of options to mitigate adverse impacts on local economies based on fisheries; e) assessing fish stocks at a regional scale; f) effectiveness of management measures on living resources;
- ∫ More research is needed on area- and resource-efficient food- and energy-production systems in coastal and shelf sea regions seen in connection with various other activities, such as Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS), tourism, and the local communities affected by these activities.
- ∫ There are insufficient observations on the deep sea. Exis-

ting observations are unevenly distributed in the region and between different marine habitats (i.e., pelagic, mesopelagic). Equal distribution of observations in the Ocean requires capacity development in all WIO States. The lack of sustained funding for observations is exacerbated by the lack of regional observation coordination within and between States and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ);

- ∫ Ocean and Human Health (OHH) is a priority knowledge gap that seeks to understand the interconnectedness of ocean and human health for mutual benefit. OHH research provides an opportunity for transdisciplinary research;
- ∫ Monitoring anthropogenic impacts on marine activities and biodiversity with pollution measurements and associated legal qualifications (organic, microplastics, noise pollution, solid waste, oil spills); and consider other anthropogenic drivers of ecosystem change (coastal urban development, artificial and urbanized development on estuaries and ports landscaping and natural resource exploitation etc.);
- ∫ More data and process studies that support robust and objective decision-making on environmental conservation, climate change effects, sustainable exploitation, coastal and ocean governance, and security are required. This includes monitoring and observing the state of pelagic and benthic systems for long term changes and increasing our ability to predict how human activities influence marine organisms and ecosystems;
- ∫ Mitigating interactions between marine megafauna and human activities;
- ∫ Relating the management of inshore freshwater environments with marine hydrology, to identify the most vulnerable areas along the coastlines to set up adaptation strategies;
- ∫ Documenting WIO aquatic and marine ecological and cultural heritage (including the offshore and distant waters and structures (e.g. seamounts and plateaus, reefs) as well as specific areas in the high seas;

Climate, governance, and regulatory aspects for ecosystems and humans

- ∫ Detailing climate change adaptation including issues related to maladaptation. More research is needed to predict the outcome of future climate scenarios and show possible cascading effects resulting from a changing WIO. There is a need to understand the consequences of various climate scenarios for questions of sovereignty, security, stability, adaptation to climate change, conservation of the WIO's pristine environment as well as maritime, leisure, exploitation, and societal and cultural questions;
- ∫ Previous WIO diagnostic reports have also made recommendations for advancing research on inter alia underwater noise, marine geohazards, valuing marine ecosystem services, and marine ecosystem modeling, which are all relevant to achieving the SDGs;
- ∫ Performing bathymetric surveys, for ocean governance interventions and purposes, and scientific advice about

Agreements and institutional arrangements for the peaceful co-management of large natural deep-sea areas and shelves (e.g the Joint Management Area tool) pending subsequent resolutions;

- ∫ Understanding certain legal qualifications relating to marine ecosystems and species, in particular the «vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs)» definition and encouraging scientific progress concerning them (descriptions, locations) in order to reduce cases of IUU fishing of VMEs or on VME sites caused by ignorance or non-compliance with the rules.

2.2. Balance between fields, ensured by the regional approach

States may regard certain scientific subjects as useful or worthy of public action and reform, while ignoring others. The Nairobi Convention Secretariat, with the assistance of the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) Science - Policy Platform (SPP) (hereafter referred to as WIO-SPP), can play a supporting role to ensure:

- a) a balanced representation of the scientific subjects that should be dealt with seamlessly in the Convention Area,
- b) that the less considered disciplines in ocean policies (e.g. benthic fauna inventories, including or not genetics) can be populated with more specialists and practitioners.

3. TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT AND TRANSFER

Marine and coastal scientific knowledge is pivotal in strategic sectors on which Small Islands Developing States (SIDS) and mainland States depend, managed by public policies or on a case-by-case basis: e.g. mariculture (site and species selection), health indicators, legal indicators about Environment Law, early warning systems on environmental threats and new risks assessment. In most cases, this can only be done if supported by dissemination of ocean knowledge dissemination, and facilitated by an adequate number of professionals, and citizens (e.g. participatory or citizen sciences).

States may be encouraged and guided whenever necessary, either by proposals from a recognised scientific stakeholder, or at their request after identifying the areas that are the most critical to them. Large and transboundary areas is an illustration of the need, vector of knowledge exchange, joint collaborations and transfer of know-how. Urgent areas of skills transfer, skills exchange and collaboration do exist.

3.1. Need for strengthening ocean and seabed special skills

Capacity building and academic curriculum on the ocean & seabed are required especially on the following skills:

- ∴ Coastal and ocean sciences for governance purposes in particular with regard to their usefulness as practical information to stakeholders;
- ∴ Data sciences for governance purposes, including Large Observatories for the Indian Ocean;
- ∴ Environmental and Law of the Sea and regulations to sustain marine development and conservation for internal, national waters and areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ);

- ∴ Marine spatial planning (MSP) to identify marine sites suitable for conservation and regulated exploitation through interdisciplinary approaches;
- ∴ Environmental economics about flows, for example the plastics flows and damage valuation;
- ∴ Environmental impact assessment (EIA) including compensation of damages caused to a maritime territory, marine protected areas and citizens, accidentally or recurrently;
- ∴ Educate and raise public awareness of ocean-related issues and preservation, to promote informed citizenship, ocean literacy, and commitment to protecting marine ecosystems.

3.2. Need for locally-based instrumentation or expensive techniques

Concerning research equipment, transferring heavy or expensive technologies to one of the countries in the region could be an option, but it involves a proper transfer of know-how, an open access to the facilities for the scientists of the region and the assignment of permanent staff attached to the facilities for the maintenance and running. The water samples analyses, or biological and genetic analyses, can be taken as examples. Otherwise, the processing of samples collected in the national waters must be done somewhere else, under specific agreements between the “Provider” State and the “Recipient” State (through public or private operators), including transfers (over a short period of time) to third-party scientific bodies having the required expertise and facilities for the analyses. Depending on legal organization, the scientific relations may vary, but most of the time they fall under the Nagoya Protocol on Access and benefit Sharing. These bilateral contractual relationships need to be specified, precise, and established under a negotiated partnership agreement. It is often highly regulated by national Law, such as the European Code of Conduct and Best Practice for Access and Benefit-Sharing. There is yet no concrete example of such issues in the ABNJ area, under the auspices of the BBNJ treaty that remains at the stage of being open to signatures for ratification.

4. DEVELOPING REGIONAL HUMAN AND INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY

Most countries rely heavily on coastal resource use and suffer from poor economic diversification. The region requires human resources (people) and institutional structures (organizations, agencies, etc.) to contribute to the region's overall ability to address various ocean challenges, implement projects, and achieve the sustainable development goals. Strengthening regional human and institutional capacity is crucial for sustainable development, effective governance, and the successful implementation of projects and policies. Scarcity of ocean science education and resources, along with gender disparity, limit the ability of each country to develop a whole spectrum of research and training excellence in key priority sectors to meet its development needs. Access to the human, institutional, technical, and financial resources needed for capacity development remains limited. For example, access to tertiary education in

ocean science and management is still unequally distributed. Financing is typically project-based and short-sighted, resulting in unsustainable outcomes once funding expires. Since individual countries often have limited resources and capacity, they may take much longer to meet ocean science and management demands on their own. Building knowledge and management capacity will require investing in a) organizational development, b) education, training, c) and fostering collaboration among various stakeholders.

4.1. Organizational & institutional development: actions by the Nairobi Convention & partners

The Nairobi Convention, WIOMSA and any regional partners have been working to strengthen regional ocean governance capacity through a comprehensive approach that includes collaboration among WIO nations and institutions, investment in science and training, and engagement with local communities and resource managers. Support from the Nairobi Convention secretariat, and “pillars” organizations such as IOC, WIOMSA (established institutions with on site a head office quarter) shall continue to encourage cooperation between research agencies, universities, technology institutes, and provide means of communication on regional exchange platforms, notably the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) Science - Policy Platform (SPP) (hereafter referred to as WIO-SPP).

WIOMSA, as an institution, created and has been implementing the Marine Science for Management (MASMA) programmes. The WIOMSA MASMA programmes started in 1995 around the premise that a regional approach in areas of marine science and management offers the most effective use of regional resources to fill the WIO region’s gap in ocean science, conservation and management capacity. WIOMSA’s MASMA programme has supported investments in marine research and management institutions through research grants and capacity development, assisting the region in developing a broad-based marine science ecosystem that covers critical areas while also resulting in economies of scale in the production of ocean science graduates. The knowledge outputs and capacity building activities from MASMA are foundational in nature and will continue to generate benefits and serve the wider scientific and management communities in the WIO region.

Other creations should be cited as other outstanding achievements: the Knowledge and competence centres. Specific knowledge and competence development centres have been established, e.i the latter (BERI) Blue Economy Research Institute as a centre for building competences hosted by the University of Seychelles (UniSey) to support research in the field of environmental sciences, specifically relating to the Blue Economy.

The University of Rhodes in South Africa has partnered with WIOMSA to offer the regional marine protected areas (MPA) management course. [Partners- BERI. University of RHODES South Africa]

To cope with the shortage of forces, all kinds of institutions (WIOMSA, CSIR, IOC, RCMRD, IRD, WIOC, Universities) may be better involved as stakeholders in marine & coastal sciences (public, private, civil society and academia). The same goes for institutional or thematic scientist networks: e.g. FARI, WIO

N.O.I.S.E. Western Indian Ocean National or International SEa-mounts, banks, submarine (Projet DIDEM³), WIoDER network Western Indian ocean Deltas Exchange & Research network⁴, among others...

4.2. Main areas of knowledge management and capacity development

This section identifies main areas of knowledge management & capacity development in the WIO context and where improvements could be made. It identifies some situations and sets of actions for each which could be launched or accelerated in the short term, supported by partners and stakeholders to ensure engagement and effective delivery in regional ocean governance. The end of this paper (Point 5) explains them.

- o Improving data sharing as a source of knowledge

WIO policy domains are becoming increasingly data driven and the challenges posed by data management need to be addressed⁵. These challenges include legal considerations, the early identification and governance of data sources, data analytics, data quality and metadata management and the proper insertion of data-driven insights into the policy-cycle. Special attention should be given to big data, which has the potential to significantly increase the region’s capabilities by allowing early detection of trends and faster feedback in support of regional policies.

In the WIO region different agencies collect data for various purposes, e.g. fishery stock assessments, and marine ecosystem studies, e.g. The Ocean Data and Information Network for Africa (ODINAFRICA)⁶ is a network hosted under the programme «International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE)» of UNESCO’s «Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission» (IOC), e.g. The Regional Centre for Mapping of Resources for Development (RCMRD⁷) to support policy dialogues, for fair and effective management and governance of protected and conserved areas in Eastern and Southern Africa as one of the regional observatories implemented by the Biodiversity and Protected Areas Management (BIOPAMA) Programme etc. [Partners: IOC UNESCO, IUCN-BIOPAMA, KMFRI].

³ <https://www.didem-project-en.org>

⁴ <https://www.wioder.org/>

⁵ see for example BARDE J., 2024, FAIR Management of marine data in the Western Indian Ocean Remote areas and in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs), Brief Scientific Policy Information, deliverable from component “High Seas, Remote and/or Deep Seabed [HS/RS/DS] & Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction [ABNJ]”, DIDEM Project, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13819928>

⁶ ODINAFRICA https://www.iode.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=31&Itemid=71

⁷ RCMRD, <https://biopama.org/a-regional-resource-hub-for-24-african-countries-officially-launched/>

Data and information are currently scattered across a multitude of disconnected systems, repositories, databases and data centres and access is often restricted.

From now on, Collaborative and strategic approaches to data acquisition and access are crucial for maximizing its value beyond its original purpose. Data and information should be made searchable, easily retrievable and as widely available as possible across the region⁸. That is why the Information Management System (IMS) is under development and included as a key pillar of implementing the ROGS.

The overall goal of the IMS is to provide a framework on how marine related information in the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) can be best collected, stored and analysed for evidence-based decision making from the local to the regional level. The vision is to make information from a wide set of local and regional initiatives available and improve settings for data sharing, harmonizing policies and legislation where relevant and access to existing databases.

IMS has to deploy a comprehensive and integrated ocean information management system, transparently, for several needs or issues for Nairobi member States. In the IMS architecture, there is a capacity development component; it considers a “human dimension” (gather, manage, analyze, disseminate informations), a “institutional capacity” (to incorporate increasing amounts of informations (big data) governance), a “political capacity” to incorporate the informations to decision-making. All designed to make an adaptive ocean. Obviously, this architecture will need to be informed from oceanic sciences input.

○ Improving collaboration methods

Favoring measures taken at regional level is a way to meet the challenges of training and increasing management capacity. Improved data collection, sharing, and application is a good example of Collaborative policymaking: they are critical to delivering integrated ocean policy and breaking down silo mentalities and approaches. Effective regional collaboration reduces duplication, enables broader inputs earlier in the policy cycle, and leads to greater strategic alignment within the organizations. Meanwhile DOIs (Digital Object Identifier) and data warehouses can be used. The steps taken at the regional level to achieve Collaborative policymaking and knowledge sharing are categorized as Programs such as the MASMA that have promoted collaborative research as the preferred working method for all levels of research. Tools to support this collaboration including meeting of grantees have been increasingly available. Senior scientists at MASMA have taken steps to encourage early career scientists to collaborate more, by setting a good example and recognizing successes. WIOMSA is reviewing MASMA to improve its knowledge-creation, use, and sharing processes.

Another innovative approach, or perspective is embodied in models of fair and equitable scientific partnership and an interdisciplinary and citizen science approach: co-design, co-delivery of science and co-learning process with partners (involving

communities, civil society, the private sector, decision-makers) through the empowerment of communities of all ages and mediation programs. This might bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and scientific understanding, underscore the importance of collaborative initiatives in ocean sciences, and “also incorporate nuanced insights provided by the local population. Mainly deployed in very coastal areas (e.g. coastal observatories to measure vulnerability to coastal erosion in Comoros, about seawater intrusion in deltas in Mozambique, deltas sedimentation in Madagascar), decisions taken are in line with the context, while being informed by good, but adapted and thrifty science. Marine Educational Areas (MEAs) associated with coral reefs are a form of action led by professional scientists, in this case aimed at sensitizing the younger generations who will become tomorrow’s decision-makers (i.e. Seychelles, Comoros).

○ Improving High Level education

WIOMSA is a good example, by many aspects, of an institution bringing together scientists from different countries and different disciplines. It mainly acts in three ways. Firstly, for more than 20 years, it has financed multidisciplinary research projects for management purposes including at least two countries in the region. Secondly, it regularly organizes (every two years until recently and now every 3 years), a regional Symposium which is now the main event to promote sea and coastal sciences in the WIO region. Thirdly, it organizes capacity building of young scientists and coastal managers through technical and methodological workshops. This effort is remarkable but as it is limited to individual actions, it can be supplemented by actions at the university level.

There is actually a gap between university training that is still poorly interdisciplinary and the management needs at local and national levels which require actors who know both marine ecosystems and the users of marine resources through the social, economic and cultural rationale which drives them. To address this gap, it is imperative that some pilot universities in the WIO region plan interdisciplinary and integrative education at the master’s level. This training could focus on understanding social ecological systems, their internal dynamics and their evolutionary trajectory. Ideally, a mainland university and an island university could test this innovative approach.

Presently, there are some very productive training courses available online (South African International Ocean Institute, etc.). There are projects including capacity building and training through research (international interdisciplinary masters programme, interprofessional summer schools, etc.). They do not cover all countries, nor all learners and researchers, often only those depending on State subsidies attached to the support project. Obviously, each initiative is an opportunity for training progress (e.g. PEPR Bridges 2024, as a French initiative), but not sufficient. An innovative approach is to explore the opportunity of a Fellowship Granting programme that combines Personal Development Programme and Targeted Research.

⁸ e.g. WIOMSA Data management plan

5. FURTHER EFFORT REQUIRED

5.1. The broad steps to be taken at regional level

The broad steps to be taken at regional level to achieve progress are numerous and classified as the following principles:

- Maintain the momentum to support regional research organizations their communications and outreach activities, and the avenues for building regional science knowledge and capacity (e.g. the WIOMSA Symposium)
- Orient science and capacity development towards ensuring that development of the WIO blue economy is informed by a sound understanding of marine and coastal systems and the role of ecosystem services in supporting resilient livelihoods and human wellbeing
- Strengthen existing regional training programs to educate coastal and marine managers on the value of knowledge management and how it contributes to effective marine spatial planning (need to include modules on information sharing, collaboration, and using knowledge management tools effectively in the current WIO MPA managers training)
- Increase competence centres for priority policy areas, and knowledge-sharing and projects in the WIO to gather and share information with relevant blue economy sectors
- Develop High Ambition knowledge and capacity Agenda for 2030 and consider a ‘Programme-based Approach
- Improve use of ‘local Ecological knowledge’ (LEK). Local people’s knowledge is ancient, spanning over thousands of years, and coming from many different cultures and is very diverse. This depth and breadth would provide significant benefits to modern science about how to manage oceans and coasts
- Promote cross-cutting cooperation between WIO member states with respect to the use and exchange of data for policy-making, including reporting; Develop the skills, tools and computing infrastructure to support a big data capability at the service of the regions political priorities and, to this end, further develop the ‘Data4Policy’ initiative (EU) and the 2024 IMS. In order to allow for possible reuse, all research projects need to be encouraged to produce data and make them available in machine-readable open formats. Encouraging transparent access to environmental data, pending accessions to the Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters (Aarhus Convention)
- Evaluate, streamline, and develop collaborative tools for policymakers and provide guidance and training to improve their efficiency:e.g. methodology to measure the impact of scientific knowledge on legislation and regulation, “legal indicators” to measure the effectiveness of the environmental

laws derived from the Nairobi Convention (e.g. CIDCE & IRD experiences).

5.2. Possible specific initiatives

Some initiatives are listed hereafter, perhaps more geared towards the Nairobi Convention Secretariat:

- calling for the specialized training in the above-mentioned fields, with the award of Nairobi Convention grants, and for the necessary length of time; one challenge is to facilitate the creation of university masters programmes by having a regional dimension ;
- increasing the scientific dialogue projects, supported and hosted by the NC secretariat, linked with initiatives from donors, and facilitating their implementation, dissemination, and reporting on them using the Nairobi Convention Clearing House Mechanism;
- structuring the regional scientific community (e.g. several ad-hoc legal and technical working group on emerging scientific matters with a balanced representation of social sciences and natural sciences, among which would be a legal group);

Its remit could include:

- a. Grants juries, awarding an annual prize (e.g. a «Julius Francis» prize) to a school, college or a higher education organization for example in three States each year, for their contribution to participatory coastal and marine science,
- b. Acting as a scientific task-force with specialist presentations on innovative or problematic subjects,
- c. Keeping vigilant, to ensure that the best available communications are used to inform, in a neutral and independent manner, about new techniques proposed here and there to enhance the ocean, or to reduce marine pollution (e.g. the issue of reducing plastic pollution by the virtues of plastics recycling and awareness campaigns with the populations...)

6. CONCLUSION

The foregoing analysis has elaborated on key actions that could be considered as priority areas in the ROGS. In summary, the aforementioned points are intended to facilitate the communication of oceanic knowledge to various representatives of the civil society and to the decision-making community («How do decision-makers and the general public access science?»). The second objective is to be better prepared for new ocean issues - through scientific dialogue - and to ensure that environmental perspectives are not regressed in the management of marine and coastal areas.